

Preliminary Evaluation of Reverberation Chamber Method for Pulsed RF Immunity Testing

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Abstract

This paper describes the evaluation of the performance characteristics of a reverberation chamber excited by pulsed rf (1.0 μ s to 10 μ s, 0.001 duty cycle) in the frequency range, 0.9 GHz to 10 GHz. The purpose of this work was to investigate the potential use of a reverberation chamber for pulsed rf immunity testing of electronic equipment. Information given includes a description of the reverberation chamber evaluated, the instrumentation used for performing the measurements, and results obtained showing the pulse dispersion characteristics of the chamber.

Introduction

Because of the significant potential of the reverberation chamber method for performing continuous wave (cw) immunity measurements, considerable interest has been expressed in determining whether this method can be extended to pulsed rf immunity testing. Measurement studies are in progress at the National Bureau of Standards (NBS) to evaluate the reverberation chamber method for pulsed rf (down to 1 μ s pulse duration) immunity testing by determining the pulse dispersion characteristics of the NBS reverberation chamber. The frequency range of interest is 0.9 GHz to 10 GHz with duty cycles down to 0.001.

Parameters of electromagnetic interference (EMI) signals that can contribute to upset in electronic equipment include: a) total energy, b) peak amplitude, and c) transient time characteristics. All these parameters are modified, relative to free-space, for signals transmitted inside a reverberation chamber. Their determination inside a reverberation chamber, particularly for pulsed rf fields, provides insight to determine calibration factors as a function of the input pulse parameters and inherent limitations associated with using this complex environment for pulsed rf immunity testing. These calibration factors and limitations are relevant to using the reverberation chamber for cw immunity testing. Details of the design, evaluation, and use of a reverberation chamber for performing cw electromagnetic immunity (susceptibility) measurements, are available [1,2,3]. These references also include estimates of the measurement uncertainties and correlation of results to free-space conditions.

Theoretical Concepts

The equivalent field strength, E_a , generated inside a reverberation chamber, for steady-state conditions, can be determined from the equation [3],

$$E_a = \sqrt{\bar{\eta} \bar{P}_d} = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{30 \bar{P}_r} \quad \text{volts/m,} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{P}_d is the "equivalent" average power density in watts/m², $\bar{\eta}$ is the average wave impedance ($\approx 120\pi$ ohms), \bar{P}_r is the average power received in watts by the reference receiving antenna terminated into 50 ohms, and λ is the wavelength in meters. The validity of (1) is based upon the assumptions that: a) the field distribution at each point in the receiving antenna aperture plane is a composite of randomly polarized plane waves, and hence, that the average response for the antennas over a 4π solid angle approaches a value as though the antenna had a gain of unity, and b) the average wave impedance is approximately equal to 120π ohms. Both of these assumptions have been shown experimentally to be true [3].

For rf pulse immunity testing, however, steady-state conditions may not be achieved inside the chamber and the transient, time-dependent field characteristics must be considered. Obviously, this field amplitude, just as in the cw steady-state case, is dependent upon the quality factor (Q) of the chamber operating as a resonant cavity. The definition of Q is given by [4]

$$Q = \frac{\text{Energy stored in the cavity}}{\text{Energy dissipated per radian}} = \frac{\omega_0 \bar{W}}{P_t}, \quad (2)$$

where ω_0 is the frequency in radians, P_t is the net power in watts transmitted into the cavity, and \bar{W} is the energy in joules stored in the cavity.

For the cw case, the chamber's composite Q, \bar{Q} , can be determined [5] from the equation,

$$\bar{Q} = \frac{3V}{2S\delta_s} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{3\lambda}{16} \left[\frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} + \frac{1}{c} \right]}, \quad (3)$$

where V is the chamber's volume in cubic meters, S is the internal surface area in square meters, $\delta_s = \sqrt{2/\omega\mu\sigma}$ is the skin depth in meters, λ is the wavelength in meters, and a, b, and c are the chamber's internal dimensions in meters. The parameters μ and σ are the permeability and conductivity of the chamber's metal walls.

The chamber's composite Q is determined by averaging the 1/Q values of all possible modes within a small frequency interval about the frequency of interest. Equation (3) is considered a maximum or upper bound because it assumes the chamber losses are due only to finite wall conductivity. In reality, some loss occurs due to leakage from the chamber, in antennas, support structures, etc., and in the chamber's wall coatings. Hence an alternative means of determining the chamber Q can be achieved from measuring the chamber's loss. Chamber loss is

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determined experimentally by measuring the difference between the net input power, P_t , delivered to the chamber's transmitting antenna, and the power available, P_r , at the reference antenna terminals. If the energy is uniformly distributed over the volume of the chamber, an empirical value, Q' , can be obtained [6] using the equation,

$$Q' = 16 \pi^2 \frac{V}{\lambda} \frac{P_r}{P_t} \quad (4)$$

where V , λ , P_t , and P_r are as previously defined.

Results obtained using (3) and (4) and the experimentally determined loss for the NBS chamber to calculate \bar{Q} and Q' are shown in figure 1. At frequencies above approximately 1 GHz the ratio of \bar{Q} to Q' approaches a constant value approximately equal to 3. This is reasonable and accounts for losses other than those due to finite wall conductivity as discussed above. The Q of the chamber increases approximately proportional to the square root of frequency

To understand what the transient response characteristics of the field excited inside the reverberation chamber are, it is useful to examine the simple theory for a one-port resonant cavity shown in figure 2 [4]. The wave's amplitudes inside (a_2 , b_2) and outside (a_1 , b_1) the cavity are described in the figure.

The coupling mechanism for the cavity may be represented by the scattering matrix,

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} \\ s_{21} & s_{22} \end{bmatrix}.$$

If a set of reference planes is selected such that both s_{11} and s_{22} are real and negative, and if the coupling is assumed to be lossless,

$$s_{11} = s_{22} = -|s_{11}| \text{ and } s_{12} = s_{21} = \pm j \sqrt{1 - |s_{11}|^2}.$$

Let $\sqrt{1 - |s_{11}|^2} = |k|$, where k is a real number (positive or negative) related to the coupling into the cavity. Then,

$$s_{11} = s_{22} = -\sqrt{1 - k^2}, \quad s_{12} = s_{21} = jk.$$

If the total attenuation for the round trip travel (twice the length, $2L$, of the cavity) is α_T in nepers, and the time required for the wave to travel the distance $2L$ is T , the transient response of the resonant cavity to a step function (a_1 just turned on) can be described as follows. Consider a_2 as a function of time as shown in figure 3. In the interval between $t = 0$ and $t = T$, $a_2 = 0$ since the signal applied at port 1 (a_1) has not traveled to the end of the cavity and been reflected back yet. At $t = T$, a_2 jumps to the value $(-jke^{-\alpha_T} a_1)$. This level is maintained as long as the source, a_1 , remains in operation. Then, this value of a_2 is reflected back to the short circuit, then back to port 1, attenuated

by $e^{-\alpha_T}$ as it travels. This fraction $\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}$ of the first step adds up in phase at $t = 2T$ and is now maintained as long as the source remains active. At $t = 3T$, the fraction $\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}$ of the second step is added up, etc., until the geometric progression shown in figure 3 is achieved. The magnitude, $|a_2|$ then, as a function of n steps, is the sum,

$$\begin{aligned} |a_2| &= ke^{-\alpha_T} [1 + (\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}) \\ &+ (\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T})^2 + \dots \\ &+ (\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T})^{n-1}] |a_1| \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\approx ke^{-\alpha_T} \left[\frac{1 - (\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T})^{t/T}}{1 - \sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}} \right] |a_1|.$$

The number of steps, n , can be replaced by t/T to obtain a "smooth" approximation as a function of t . The final amplitude of a_2 , $|a_2|_{\text{final}} = A_2$ is

$$A_2 = \frac{k e^{-\alpha_T} |a_1|}{1 - \sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}}.$$

The time constant (charge time), τ_c , at which $|a_2| = (1 - 1/e) A_2$ is approximately $\tau_c = 2Q/\omega_0$. This is similar to the time constant for a lumped constant equivalent RC circuit. Recall that $1/Q = 1/Q_u + 1/Q_e$, where Q_u is the unload (chamber empty) Q of the cavity and Q_e is the Q external to the cavity. For critical coupling, $Q_u = Q_e$ (steady state conditions). During the transient condition shown in figure 3, $Q_e > Q_u$.

As a function of time, b_1 (the outgoing wave) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \left\{ -\sqrt{1 - k^2} \right. \\ &+ k^2 e^{-\alpha_T} \left[\frac{1 - (\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T})^{t/T}}{1 - \sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}} \right] \left. \right\} a_1. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

If $\sqrt{1 - k^2}$ can be neglected, the final value (steady state conditions) of $b_1 = B_1$, at $t \gg \tau_c$ is

$$B_1 = \frac{k^2 e^{-\alpha_T}}{1 - \sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha_T}} a_1.$$

If the source, a_1 , is turned off (after the field inside the cavity has reached steady-state conditions), the signal inside the cavity collapses in a stair step fashion as shown in figure 4. At time $t' = 0^+$, assuming $t = 0$ at turn off of a_1 , $b_1 = B_1$. Then at time $t' = (0 + T)^+$, b_1 will decrease by

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the factor $\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha T}$, since the wave within the cavity is no longer replenished. At subsequent intervals of duration T , b_1 will drop by the factor $\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha T}$. The smooth approximation to the resulting geometric progression for b_1 is given as

$$b_1 = B_1 (\sqrt{1 - k^2} e^{-\alpha T})^{t'/T}, \quad (7)$$

where t'/T has been substituted for n . Again, the time constant (decay time), τ_d , is approximately $2Q/\omega$. For this condition, $Q_u > Q_e$.

If the source is turned on for a short interval and then turned off, as occurs for pulsed rf, the field inside the cavity can be determined by combining (6) and (7) realizing that the time reference ($t = t' = 0$) for each equation is relative to when the source, a_1 , is turn on or off. The final form is dependent upon the length of the pulse burst and the time constant (charge or decay) of the cavity.

The composite field due to the combining of modes inside a reverberation chamber, excited by pulsed rf, will be similar in form to that obtained for the simple cavity, assuming that the principle of superposition applies. The field at any given point in the chamber will be a composite of all existing modes, each contributing vectorially as a function of the individual Q and resonance condition. Experimental results shown later in this paper demonstrate that the transient wave form of the received energy in the NBS reverberation chamber excited with pulsed rf indeed is similar to that predicted by a combination of (6) and (7) as shown in figures 3 and 4.

System Description

Cross sectional views of the NBS reverberation chamber showing the placements of its tuner, transmitting antennas, and receiving antennas for evaluating its rf pulse response characteristics are shown in figure 5. The basic measurement system is shown in figure 6. The test field is established by means of a pulsed rf source connected to a broadband transmitting antenna positioned in the corner of the chamber. The antenna is oriented toward the corner to scatter the transmitted signal in all directions and hence as uniformly as possible into all existing modes. Modes excited are stirred by rotating the tuner which functions as a field-perturbing device. The receiving antenna is also a broadband antenna positioned at and oriented toward another corner of the chamber. This antenna arrangement minimizes direct coupling of energy between the two antennas or directly into or out of the chamber's test zone. Software code controls the signal measurement and digitizing instrumentation to allow recording of the pulse waveforms delivered to the chamber's transmitting antenna and received by the chamber's receiving antenna. The computer also controls the movement of the tuner in discrete steps. The instrumentation used is capable of measuring signals with rise times in the order of 30 ps at a sampling rate of 50 kHz/s and sample sizes up to 1024.

Measurements were made, at the frequencies of interest, for each position of the chamber's tuner at 200 incremental tuner positions per complete revolution (1.8 degree increments). The waveform data were then processed to determine the statistical parameters as a function of time. The antennas used were a matched pair of rectangular single ridged horns designed to operate in the frequency range 0.8 - 12 GHz. Examples of the results of these measurements are shown in figures 7 to 9. Figure 7 shows the statistical parameters of the received pulse waveforms obtained at 6 frequencies for 10 μ s input pulse durations. These graphs give an indication of the time required for the chamber to charge up to its steady state amplitude based upon the chamber's Q . Charge up refers to the time required for the input signal, radiated from the source antenna, to complete all significant multiple reflections that contribute to the final field inside the chamber. Figure 8 shows similar data grouped by input pulse duration at selected frequencies. Each graph in figures 7 and 8 shows two curves, one for the maximum and one for the average received signals, determined from 200 tuner positions for one complete tuner revolution as a function of time. By examining this type of data at a number of selected frequencies, the approximate charge time can be determined as a function of frequency as shown in figure 9. The implication of figure 9 is that the pulse duration versus frequency should be above the curve for using the chamber for radiated rf pulse immunity testing. For example, a pulse duration of greater than or equal to 3 μ s should be used at 2.9 GHz to avoid significant errors resulting from distortion of the test signal inside the chamber. This is necessary in order for the exposure field to arrive at steady-state values so the results can be expressed in terms of equivalent cw testing analysis.

Because these measurements are very data intensive and require large computer memory and measurement time, it was necessary to restrict the number of tuner steps. Additional measurements were made at one selected frequency, 2.9 GHz, using a greater number of steps to determine the magnitude of error introduced by this limitation. These results are shown in the figure 10. The increase in the peak amplitude from 200 to 400 samples is less than 0.5 dB.

Summary

In summary, a few observations resulting from this study are worth mentioning. First, the time required for the pulse wave amplitude to rise to its steady-state value inside the chamber (chamber charge time) and to decay to zero after the input signal is removed (decay time) can be theoretically predicted as discussed earlier in this paper. As expected, they are a function of frequency and chamber Q . The rise and decay times decrease approximately proportional to the square root of frequency as the frequency increases. This is in agreement with what was theoretically predicted since the Q of the chamber (figure 1) increases approximately proportional to the square root of frequency so that $\tau_c = \tau_d = 2Q/\omega_0$. The field inside the chamber is also a function of the chamber loss which is dependent upon the chamber's Q . (The field is a function of the energy dissipated in the walls, support structures, antennas, etc, as well as the stored energy in the chamber.) Implied above is that

the charge and decay times of the chamber could be reduced by artificially lowering the Q, for example by inserting a small amount of rf absorber. However, this would be at the expense of reduced accuracy in the ability to determine the test field amplitude. Work is progressing to determine how serious this trade off is (i.e., how large the errors could be from using the chamber with input pulse durations shorter than the chamber charge time) and to investigate other potential limitations for using the reverberation chamber for pulsed rf immunity testing.

References

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Figure 1. Theoretical composite Q and experimental Q determined for NBS reverberation chamber.

Figure 2. One-port cavity.

Figure 3. Build-up of cavity wave a_2 as a function of time.

Figure 4. Transient response to collapsed input.

Figure 5. Cross sectional views of NBS reverberation chamber for use in evaluating response to rf pulsed fields.

NBS Reverberation Chamber
(3.048 x 2.76 x 4.577m)

Figure 6. Block diagram of system for evaluating pulsed rf response characteristics of reverberation chamber.

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Figure 7. Statistical amplitude distribution (maximum and average) of the rf pulse waveforms inside the NBS reverberation chamber measured using a rectangular, single ridged horn. Input pulse duration = 10 μ sec at 0.9, 1.3, 2.9, 5.65, 8.9, and 10 GHz. Duty cycle = 0.001.

Figure 8. Statistical amplitude distribution of the rf pulse waveform inside the NBS reverberation chamber measured using a rectangular, single ridged horn. Data shown at 2.9 GHz for rf input pulse durations of 1, 3, 5, and 10 usec. Duty cycle = 0.001.

Figure 9. Estimated time required for rf signal injected into the MBS reverberation chamber to reach maximum amplitude as a function of frequency. Data derived from figures 7 and 8.

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Figure 10. Comparison between the received rf pulse statistical parameters (maximum and average) determined from 200 and 400 tuner positions per revolution at 2.9 GHz.